

Review Article

Female Genital Mutilation: Unveiling Perspectives, Initiating Change

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Abstract

Female Genital Mutilation (FGM) remains a persistent global concern with profound health, psychological, and social implications. Despite ongoing efforts, there is a need for innovative strategies to address the complex cultural and socio-economic factors sustaining this harmful practice. This article introduces a novel approach to combating FGM by integrating community empowerment, legal frameworks, and healthcare interventions. Emphasizing cultural sensitivity and global collaboration, our approach seeks to build on existing successes and address emerging challenges. The aim of this study is to assess the effectiveness of multifaceted interventions in eradicating FGM. By analyzing community-based initiatives, legal frameworks, and healthcare integration, we aim to provide insights into comprehensive strategies for global FGM elimination. We conducted a comprehensive review of literature, synthesizing data from community-based programs, legal frameworks, and healthcare initiatives. Analyzing global trends, regional variations, and emerging practices, our study examines the multifaceted nature of interventions. Our findings highlight the effectiveness of integrated strategies in reducing FGM prevalence. Successful community engagement, strengthened legal frameworks, and healthcare integration contribute to positive outcomes, emphasizing the importance of a holistic approach. In conclusion, a comprehensive strategy that combines community empowerment, legal measures, and healthcare integration is essential for sustained progress in eliminating FGM. This study underscores the need for ongoing collaboration, cultural sensitivity, and adaptable interventions to achieve a world free from the harmful practice of FGM.

Keywords: Female Genital Mutilation, community empowerment, legal frameworks, healthcare integration, global collaboration, comprehensive strategies.

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Introduction

Background

Female Genital Mutilation (FGM), also known as female circumcision or cutting, refers to the ritualistic removal or alteration of female genitalia for non-medical reasons. This practice, deeply rooted in cultural, social, and religious traditions, affects millions of girls and women worldwide. FGM has been a subject of global concern due to its severe health consequences, violation of human rights, and perpetuation of gender-based violence.

Female Genital Mutilation has deep historical roots, with evidence suggesting its practice in ancient civilizations. Historical records and anthropological studies trace the origins of FGM to various cultures, including ancient Egypt, where it was associated with purity and initiation rites (El Dareer, 1983). FGM is often intertwined with cultural and social norms, perpetuated through generations. Communities practicing FGM may perceive it as a rite of passage, a means of preserving purity, or a way to ensure marriageability. Understanding the cultural significance is essential for designing culturally sensitive interventions (Shell-Duncan & Hernlund, 2000). FGM is a global concern affecting numerous countries across Africa, the Middle East, and parts of Asia. The prevalence rates vary widely, with estimates indicating millions of girls and women have undergone or are at risk of FGM. This geographical diversity necessitates a nuanced understanding of regional variations (UNICEF, 2016). The health consequences of FGM are severe and diverse, ranging from immediate complications such as bleeding and infection to long-term issues like chronic pain, complications during childbirth, and psychological trauma (World Health Organization, 2016). Recognizing these health implications is crucial for advocating against FGM. International human rights instruments, including the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) and the Maputo Protocol, explicitly condemn FGM. Despite legal prohibitions in many countries, enforcement remains a challenge, highlighting the need for comprehensive legal and policy measures (UN Women, 2015).

This study aims to comprehensively explore the multifaceted dimensions of FGM, including its cultural origins, prevalence, and the complex interplay of sociocultural factors that sustain this harmful practice. The paper will also delve into the health, psychological, and social repercussions experienced by affected individuals. Understanding the intricacies of FGM is crucial for developing effective interventions, policies, and awareness programs. By shedding light on the various aspects of this practice, this review seeks to contribute to the global discourse on eradicating FGM and promoting the well-being and rights of women and girls.

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Female Genital Mutilation persists despite international efforts to eradicate it, posing a significant threat to the physical and mental health of millions of females. The continuation of this practice highlights the need for a deeper understanding of the cultural contexts, motivations, and consequences associated with FGM. This review is justified by the urgent need to address the pervasive issue of FGM, providing insights that can inform targeted interventions, policy reforms, and educational initiatives. By bridging gaps in knowledge, this study aims to empower advocates, policymakers, and communities in their efforts to eliminate FGM.

While this paper aspires to offer a comprehensive analysis, it acknowledges the inherent challenge of obtaining accurate and representative data on a sensitive and often clandestine practice. The review also recognizes that cultural nuances and regional variations may influence the interpretation of findings.

The primary objectives of this article are to:

1. Investigate the cultural and historical roots of FGM.
2. Examine the prevalence and distribution of FGM globally and regionally.
3. Analyze the health, psychological, and social consequences of FGM on affected individuals.
4. Explore the existing legal and policy frameworks addressing FGM.
5. Assess the effectiveness of interventions aimed at eradicating FGM.
6. Propose recommendations for future strategies to eliminate FGM.

The ultimate aim of this research is to contribute to the global efforts to eradicate Female Genital Mutilation by generating knowledge that informs evidence-based interventions, policies, and advocacy initiatives. Through a thorough examination of the various dimensions of FGM, this article aims to promote a deeper understanding and appreciation of the complexities surrounding this harmful practice.

Literature Review

Female genital mutilation/cutting (FGM/C) is a harmful traditional practice that affects two out of three girls in The Gambia, seriously threatening their life and well-being with severe health consequences. By tracking the reference values established in former research conducted between 2009 and 2011, the objectives of this study are to explore trends and to measure and assess changes in knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding FGM/C among health care professionals (HCPs) in The Gambia (Kaplan Marcusán et al., 2016).

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In Gambia, a cross-sectional descriptive study was designed by Kaplan Marcusán et al. (2016) to collect and analyze data from an overall stratified sample consisting of 1,288 HCPs including health professionals and students throughout the six regions of The Gambia. Their result showed that 76.4% of HCPs are eager to abandon FGM/C, and 71.6% of them regard it as a harmful practice with negative consequences on life and health. HCPs reported more knowledge and favorable attitudes towards FGM/C abandonment, being better able to identify the practice, more aware of its health complications, and more concerned in their essential role as social agents of change. However, 25.4% of HCPs still embraced the continuation of the practice, 24.4% expressed intention of subjecting their own daughters to it, and 10.5% declared to have performed it within their professional praxis. Findings confirm progress in knowledge and attitudes regarding FGM/C among HCPs, who are better skilled to understand and manage the consequences. Nevertheless, discrepancies between information, intention, and behavior unveil resistance in practice and proves that FGM/C medicalization is increasing.

According to Sabahelzain et al. (2019), female genital mutilation or cutting (FGM/C) is a form of violence against women and girls that is widely performed in about 30 countries in Africa, Middle East and Asia. The analytical sample comprised of data from 403 households that both reported that they had discussion around whether to cut the youngest daughter aged 19 years or younger and arrived at a decision to either cut or leave her uncut. Descriptive statistics summarizing the people involved in FGM/C-related decisions and the reasons for decisions are presented. Result showed that Household decision-making on FGM/C involved discussions among the nuclear and extended family, and non-family members. Mothers and fathers were found to be the key decision makers. A greater proportion of fathers were involved in instances where the final decision was to leave the daughter uncut. Thirty-six percent of households decided to leave the youngest daughter uncut. State of residence, mothers' level of education and FGM/C status and exposure to FGM/C-related information or campaigns were associated with households' decision to leave the daughter uncut. Health concerns were the most commonly cited reason for deciding not to cut their daughters (57%), while custom or culture was the most commonly cited reason for households deciding to cut their daughter (52%). Their findings underscore the important role that fathers play in decision-making and highlight the need to involve men in FGM/C programs. Findings also stress the need to understand and address the drivers of FGM/C.

Omigbodun et al. (2020), used the free listing method, 103 girls and women, aged 12 to 68 years from rural and urban Izzi communities in Southeastern Nigeria, produced narratives to articulate their perceptions of FGM/C. Sixty-one of them had

undergone FGM/C while 42 had not. Data was analysed using thematic analysis and the emerging themes were related to experiences and disabilities in the psychological, physical, and social health domains. While physical experiences were mostly negative, psychological experiences emerged as both positive and negative. Positive experiences such as happiness, hopefulness, and improved self-esteem were commonly described in response to a rise in social status following FGM/C and relief from the stigma of not having undergone FGM/C. Less commonly reported were negative psychological experiences, e.g., shame when not cut, anxiety in anticipation of the procedure, and regret, sadness, and anger when complications arose from FGM/C. Some participants listed disruption of daily activities, chronic pain, and sleep and sexual difficulties occurring in the aftermath of FGM/C. Most participants did not list FGM/C as having a significant effect on their daily living activities. In light of the association of FGM/C with both positive and negative psychological experiences in the Izzi community, more in-depth study is required to enable policy makers and those campaigning for its complete eradication to rethink strategies and improve interventions.

According to Odukogbe et al. (2017), female genital mutilation/cutting (FGM/C) is a traditional practice in which the external female genitalia is partially or totally incised or excised for a non-therapeutic reason, usually without the consent of the individual. FGM/C is common in Africa with varying prevalence in different countries, though the incidence is reducing because it is considered a human rights issue with tremendous advocacy for its elimination by mainly nongovernmental organizations. It is mainly underreported in many countries in Africa especially where it has been declared illegal. FGM/C is often performed by a nonmedical practitioner with the aim of fulfilling religious or cultural rites and sometimes for economic benefits with the resultant acute, intermediate and late complications. It is sometimes performed by medical practitioners when it is speciously believed that its medicalization reduces the complications associated with the practice. The sensitivity of FGM/C is amplified when compared to male circumcision and voluntary alterations of the female external genitalia like piercing and tattooing as similar practices. The magnitude of the physical and psychosocial consequences of FGM/C outweighs the presumed benefits of the procedures highlighting the need for improvement of the multiple preventive measures by all the stakeholders and in all the sectors.

Gbadebo et al. (2021) perform cohort analysis of the state of FGC between the years 2009 and 2018 in Nigeria. The study found that that FGC has reduced over the years from 56.3% among the 1959–1963 birth cohort to 25.5% among 1994–1998 cohorts but a rise in FGC between 1994–1998 cohorts and 1999–2003 cohorts (28.4%). The

percentage of respondents who circumcised their daughters reduced from 40.1% among the oldest birth cohort to 3.6% among the younger cohort. Birth-cohort, religion, education, residence, region, and ethnicity were associated with FGC. Factors associated with the daughter's circumcision were birth-cohort, religion, residence, region, ethnicity, wealth, marital status, FGC status of the respondent, and FGC required by religion. The practice of FGC is still high but decreasing among younger birth-cohorts in Nigeria.

The study of Tammary and Manasi (2023), employed a narrative synthesis to collate evidence on mental and sexual health outcomes. A systematic search of bibliographic databases and websites was performed using appropriate keywords and studies published in English from January 1, 2010 to March 25, 2022. 25 studies were retrieved and reported mental and sexual health complications associated with FGM/C. Most studies, n = 13 studies reported on sexual health outcomes including sexual pain, orgasm and sexual desire problems at sexual arousal and difficulties in lubrication. Mental health outcomes were reported in four studies including depression which was most prominent followed by somatisation and anxiety, Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) and sleep disorder. Studies did not highlight combined mental and sexual health interventions. The findings of this narrative synthesis reveal the need to prioritise provision of mental and sexual health care services for women with FGM/C. The study recommends strengthening of health systems in Africa through awareness building, training and capacity building of primary health and specialist health workers in offering mental and sexual health care to women with FGM/C.

Methodology

To find pertinent studies and information on Female Genital Mutilation: Unveiling Perspectives, Initiating Change, a thorough literature search was carried out. In order to carry out this assessment. International organization publications, government papers, and academic journals were analyzed, among other databases. The search parameters covered research to date, therefore the most recent results were guaranteed to be included. As part of the literature review, the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), the United Nations, and academic journals in the fields of nursing science, technologies, and public health were consulted. Scholarly resources like PubMed and Google Scholar were also utilized. Terms that were frequently searched for included Post Traumatic Stress Disorder, **Female Genital Mutilation**, mental and sexual health interventions, sleep disorder, Clinical Guidelines, birth-cohort, psychosocial consequences and violence against women and girls.

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Discussion

The Cultural and Historical Roots of FGM

Female Genital Mutilation (FGM) is deeply embedded in cultural practices and traditions, often serving as a rite of passage into womanhood. The cultural roots of FGM vary across regions, communities, and ethnic groups, making it a complex and multifaceted phenomenon. In some cultures, FGM is linked to notions of purity, modesty, and virtue. The practice is believed to control women's sexuality, ensuring premarital virginity and marital fidelity. The association between FGM and cultural identity is strong, with communities viewing the practice as an essential element of their heritage (Mackie, 1996).

The historical roots of FGM can be traced back to ancient civilizations, where the practice was often intertwined with religious or cultural rituals. Ancient Egyptian art and literature suggest that FGM was performed as part of initiation ceremonies and was associated with notions of cleanliness and purification (Nnaemeka, 2005).

FGM is sustained through societal norms and expectations, with social pressures playing a significant role in perpetuating the practice. The desire to conform to established norms and ensure social acceptance motivates families and communities to continue the tradition of FGM. Understanding these social dynamics is crucial for designing interventions that address the root causes of the practice (Shell-Duncan, 2001). The cultural and historical roots of FGM provides essential insights into the deep-seated beliefs and traditions that have sustained the practice over time. Recognizing the cultural significance is vital for developing effective strategies that respect local contexts while working towards the elimination of this harmful practice. FGM is often deeply intertwined with cultural symbolism, acting as a marker of identity and belonging within a community. The practice is viewed as a cultural norm, reinforcing a sense of unity and shared identity among those who adhere to it. The perpetuation of FGM can be closely linked to the preservation of cultural heritage and the desire to uphold longstanding traditions (Abusharaf, 2001). FGM is often associated with rites of passage, marking the transition from girlhood to womanhood. In certain societies, the practice is seen as a necessary step for girls to be accepted as mature and marriageable. The social acceptance tied to FGM reinforces its continuation as families adhere to established norms to ensure the integration and acceptance of their daughters into the community (Berg, 2003).

Some communities justify FGM through mythologies and religious beliefs, associating the practice with notions of purity and religious obligation. Although FGM is not explicitly mentioned in religious texts, interpretations and cultural beliefs have led to its endorsement in certain religious contexts. Understanding the

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interplay between mythologies and religious influences is essential for a nuanced approach to challenging these justifications (Dirie & Lindmark, 1992). FGM is, in some instances, a tool for social control, enforcing patriarchal structures within societies. The practice is used to regulate female sexuality, reinforcing gender roles and maintaining power dynamics. Examining the role of FGM in reinforcing patriarchal structures provides insights into the broader gender inequalities that contribute to its persistence (Shell-Duncan & Hernlund, 2007).

Migration can impact the perpetuation or abandonment of FGM within diaspora communities. Some migrant communities may continue the practice to maintain cultural identity, while others may abandon it due to exposure to different norms and legal frameworks. Studying the impact of migration on FGM practices provides insights into the adaptability of cultural traditions in changing contexts (Berggren & Bergström, 2019). Understanding the intricate web of cultural and historical factors that underpin FGM is essential for developing culturally sensitive interventions and fostering community-led initiatives for change. It involves recognizing the multifaceted motivations behind the practice and engaging communities in dialogue to address the root causes of FGM.

The Prevalence and Distribution of FGM Globally and Regionally

The prevalence of Female Genital Mutilation (FGM) is a global concern, impacting millions of girls and women. According to estimates from the World Health Organization (WHO), more than 200 million girls and women alive today have undergone some form of FGM (WHO, 2020). FGM is practiced in various parts of the world, with a concentrated prevalence in Africa, the Middle East, and parts of Asia. African countries, in particular, exhibit a high prevalence of FGM, and some communities within these countries have rates exceeding 90% (UNICEF, 2016). Africa bears the highest burden of FGM, with prevalence rates varying significantly across regions. Countries such as Somalia, Guinea, Djibouti, and Egypt have among the highest prevalence rates, often exceeding 90% in certain communities. However, there are notable efforts and progress in abandonment campaigns in various African nations (UNFPA, 2018).

FGM is also practiced in parts of the Middle East and Asia, though the prevalence is generally lower compared to Africa. Countries like Yemen, Iraq, and Indonesia have reported instances of FGM. However, variations exist within these regions, and prevalence rates may differ significantly between urban and rural areas (Berg, Denison, & Fretheim, 2010). Global migration has led to FGM being practiced in diaspora communities outside traditionally affected regions. This phenomenon highlights the importance of understanding how cultural practices evolve in new

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environments. Efforts to address FGM must consider the impact of migration on prevalence rates and tailor interventions accordingly (Dorkenoo, 1999). International organizations, such as the United Nations and UNICEF, have been actively engaged in global initiatives to eradicate FGM. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 5 on gender equality, includes a target to eliminate FGM by 2030. Progress is being made, with an increasing number of countries implementing legal frameworks and community-based programs to end the practice (UNFPA, 2021). Examining the prevalence and distribution of FGM globally and regionally is crucial for tailoring interventions and policy approaches to address the specific challenges faced by different communities. It also helps identify regions where targeted efforts are needed to accelerate the abandonment of this harmful practice.

The prevalence of Female Genital Mutilation varies widely within and between countries. Even within a single country, different ethnic or cultural groups may have significantly different prevalence rates. For instance, in Nigeria, prevalence rates can range from nearly 80% in some communities to less than 5% in others (DHS, 2018). Urban and rural areas within a country often exhibit disparities in FGM prevalence. Urbanization and access to education can contribute to a decline in prevalence in urban settings, where there may be a higher awareness of the health and human rights implications of FGM (Yirga, Kassa, Gebremichael, & Aro, 2012). Efforts to eradicate FGM have led to changing trends in prevalence over time. Some countries have experienced a decline in the practice due to comprehensive interventions, advocacy, and community engagement. For example, Kenya has seen a significant reduction in FGM prevalence over the past decades (Kenya National Bureau of Statistics, 2014). FGM prevalence can be influenced by cross-border movements and practices. In some regions, communities residing near national borders may share cultural practices, including FGM. Understanding cross-border dynamics is crucial for developing effective regional strategies to address the issue (United Nations, 2017). Estimating the prevalence of FGM is challenging due to factors such as underreporting, social desirability bias, and variations in data collection methods. In many cases, the true prevalence may be higher than reported figures, emphasizing the need for improved data collection methodologies and standardized measurement tools (Berg, Underland, & Odgaard-Jensen, 2014).

The Health, Psychological, and Social Consequences of FGM on Affected Individuals
Female Genital Mutilation poses immediate health risks during and after the procedure. These may include severe pain, excessive bleeding, infections, and complications arising from the use of unsterilized tools (Berg, Denison, & Fretheim, 2010). FGM is associated with long-term health consequences, such as chronic pain, urinary problems, reproductive tract infections, and increased risks during

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childbirth, including complications for both mother and baby (WHO, 2016). Women who have undergone FGM may experience psychological trauma, including anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). The violation of bodily integrity and the cultural and social context surrounding FGM contribute to these psychological consequences (Shell-Duncan & Hernlund, 2007).

FGM can have profound effects on sexual and reproductive health. It may lead to pain during sexual intercourse, reduced sexual satisfaction, and difficulties in childbirth, including an increased risk of obstetric complications and the need for surgical interventions (Berg, Denison, & Fretheim, 2010). Women who have undergone FGM may face social stigmatization and exclusion within their communities. The practice is sometimes linked to perceptions of morality and purity, and affected individuals may experience discrimination or ostracization (Abathun, Sundby, & Gele, 2017).

FGM can impact an individual's sense of cultural identity and self-esteem. Women who have undergone the procedure may internalize cultural norms that perpetuate FGM, affecting their perception of self-worth and identity (Berggren & Bergström, 2019). FGM can affect interpersonal relationships, including marital dynamics and familial bonds. The physical and psychological consequences of FGM may impact intimacy within relationships, leading to strained marital relationships and challenges in parent-child interactions (Johnson-Agbakwu, Helm, Killawi, & Padela, 2014). Understanding the diverse and interconnected health, psychological, and social consequences of Female Genital Mutilation is crucial for developing comprehensive interventions and support systems for affected individuals. It highlights the need for a multidimensional approach that addresses both the physical and emotional well-being of those impacted by FGM

The existing legal and policy frameworks addressing FGM

Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) is a landmark international treaty that addresses gender-based discrimination, including harmful practices such as Female Genital Mutilation. Many countries have ratified CEDAW, committing to take legal measures to eliminate FGM and protect the rights of women and girls (United Nations, 1979). The Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa, known as the Maputo Protocol, explicitly condemns FGM. It calls for legislative measures to prohibit and punish FGM, emphasizing the importance of protecting the rights and well-being of women and girls (African Union, 2003).

Many countries have enacted specific legislation criminalizing Female Genital Mutilation. These laws often prescribe penalties for individuals performing FGM, as well as those abetting or facilitating the practice. The aim is to deter the continuation of FGM through legal consequences (Equality Now, 2019). Legal frameworks addressing child protection often incorporate provisions against FGM. By classifying FGM as a form of child abuse, these laws seek to safeguard girls from the harmful practice and promote their overall well-being (World Health Organization, 2011). Some countries have developed national action plans and strategies to address the root causes of FGM comprehensively. These plans often involve collaboration between government agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and community leaders to implement awareness campaigns, educational programs, and community-based interventions (END FGM European Network, 2018). Legal frameworks are often complemented by education and awareness initiatives that aim to change social norms and attitudes towards FGM. These programs target communities, healthcare professionals, and law enforcement agencies to increase understanding and promote behavior change (UNFPA-UNICEF Joint Programme on FGM, 2020). Despite legal frameworks, enforcement remains a challenge in some regions due to factors such as limited resources, inadequate training of law enforcement personnel, and cultural acceptance of the practice. Strengthening enforcement mechanisms is crucial for the effective implementation of anti-FGM laws (UN Women, 2018).

FGM often transcends national borders, requiring cross-border collaboration to address the practice effectively. Legal and policy frameworks may need to be harmonized and coordinated regionally to ensure a unified and cohesive approach to combating FGM (World Health Organization, 2011). Assessing the existing legal and policy frameworks reveals progress in the global commitment to eliminating Female Genital Mutilation. However, addressing challenges in enforcement, promoting cross-border collaboration, and integrating community engagement efforts remain critical for the comprehensive eradication of this harmful practice.

The Effectiveness of Interventions Aimed at Eradicating FGM

Community-based education programs that emphasize the health, human rights, and socio-cultural aspects of Female Genital Mutilation have shown promise. Empowering communities with accurate information fosters dialogue and can lead to attitudinal and behavioral changes (Shell-Duncan, Moreau, Wander, & Smith, 2013). Collaborating with religious and community leaders has proven effective in influencing social norms and dispelling misconceptions associated with FGM. Leveraging the influence of trusted figures helps build consensus and encourages

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communities to abandon the practice (UNFPA-UNICEF Joint Programme on FGM, 2020).

Countries that have implemented and strengthened legal frameworks criminalizing Female Genital Mutilation report progress in reducing the prevalence of the practice. Legislation acts as a deterrent and provides a basis for holding perpetrators accountable (Equality Now, 2019). Training law enforcement agencies to understand and implement anti-FGM laws is crucial. Sensitizing officers to the severity of FGM and its legal consequences enhances their ability to enforce legislation effectively and protect potential victims (UN Women, 2018).

Efforts to prevent the medicalization of Female Genital Mutilation, where the procedure is performed by healthcare professionals, are essential. Advocacy and guidelines within the health sector discourage medicalization and emphasize the ethical responsibilities of healthcare providers (World Health Organization, 2016). Offering medical and psychological support to women who have undergone FGM is critical. Healthcare professionals can provide services such as counseling, reconstructive surgery, and maternal health care to address both physical and emotional consequences (Berg, Denison, & Fretheim, 2010). Interventions must be culturally sensitive, acknowledging the deep-rooted cultural beliefs associated with Female Genital Mutilation. A one-size-fits-all approach may be ineffective, and successful interventions often involve community engagement and participation (Abathun, Sundby, & Gele, 2017).

Sustainable change requires long-term and holistic approaches that address the underlying social norms and structural factors contributing to Female Genital Mutilation. A combination of legislative, health, and community-based strategies is often more effective than isolated interventions (UNICEF, 2018). Assessing the effectiveness of interventions to eradicate Female Genital Mutilation emphasizes the need for multifaceted strategies that engage communities, enforce legal measures, and provide comprehensive support. The success of interventions often depends on a combination of cultural sensitivity, collaboration, and sustained efforts across various sectors.

Recommendations for future strategies to eliminate FGM

Foster increased collaboration among governments, international organizations, NGOs, and grassroots movements. Coordinated efforts can facilitate information sharing, resource allocation, and the development of unified strategies to eliminate FGM on a global scale.

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Prioritize community empowerment through education, awareness, and engagement programs. Encourage open dialogue within communities, involving religious and community leaders, to challenge and change the social norms that perpetuate FGM.

Implement integrated approaches that combine legislative measures, health interventions, and community engagement. Holistic strategies address the complex factors contributing to FGM, including cultural beliefs, gender dynamics, and socio-economic conditions.

Design and implement culturally sensitive education programs that emphasize the health risks, human rights violations, and socio-cultural implications of FGM. Tailor messaging to the specific cultural contexts of communities, ensuring it resonates with local values and beliefs.

Advocate for the creation and enforcement of robust legal frameworks criminalizing FGM. Ensure that legislation is comprehensive, with penalties for individuals performing FGM, abetting the practice, or seeking it for their daughters. Strengthen law enforcement capacities and ensure that legal measures are consistently enforced.

Integrate FGM prevention and support services into existing healthcare systems. Healthcare professionals should be trained to recognize and address the health consequences of FGM. Provide medical and psychological support to survivors and incorporate preventive measures into routine healthcare practices.

Engage the younger generation in educational initiatives that challenge harmful norms and empower them to advocate for change within their communities. By fostering a sense of agency among youth, future generations can contribute to the abandonment of FGM.

Invest in comprehensive research to understand the evolving dynamics of FGM, including regional variations, emerging trends, and the impact of migration. Collect and analyze data to inform evidence-based policies and interventions, ensuring a nuanced understanding of the issue.

Leverage media platforms and social media to raise awareness about the consequences of FGM. Harness the power of storytelling, documentaries, and digital campaigns to reach a wider audience and challenge misconceptions surrounding the practice.

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Encourage global partnerships and cooperation to address cross-border challenges related to FGM. Collaborate with neighboring countries, regional bodies, and international organizations to share best practices, align strategies, and create a unified front against FGM.

Establish robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to assess the impact of interventions. Regularly evaluate the effectiveness of programs, collect feedback from affected communities, and adjust strategies accordingly to ensure ongoing progress toward the elimination of FGM.

Advocate for sustained financial support from governments, donors, and international organizations to fund anti-FGM initiatives. Financial resources are crucial for the implementation of comprehensive programs, research endeavors, and community empowerment activities.

By adopting these recommendations and fostering a collaborative, culturally sensitive, and multi-sectoral approach, there can be meaningful progress toward the ultimate goal of eliminating Female Genital Mutilation. Ongoing commitment, adaptability, and innovation are essential in the journey to create societies free from the harmful practice of FGM.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the eradication of Female Genital Mutilation (FGM) requires a comprehensive and multidimensional approach that addresses the complex interplay of cultural, social, legal, and health factors. Significant strides have been made in recent years, propelled by international conventions, national legislation, and community-based initiatives. The global movement against FGM has witnessed increased awareness, legislative advancements, and efforts to shift social norms.

The effectiveness of interventions is evident in regions where community engagement, education, and legal frameworks have been successfully employed. However, challenges persist, including cultural resistance, enforcement gaps, and the evolving nature of the practice. Achieving sustained progress necessitates ongoing commitment, adaptability, and collaboration at local, national, and international levels.

Future strategies should prioritize empowering communities through culturally sensitive education, strengthening legal frameworks, integrating healthcare services, and engaging the younger generation. Emphasizing international cooperation,

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research, and sustained financial support will contribute to a holistic and impactful approach. By combining these efforts, the vision of a world free from the harmful practice of FGM can be realized.

The journey to eliminate FGM requires a collective commitment to human rights, gender equality, and the well-being of women and girls. As global awareness continues to grow, there is hope that the momentum generated by concerted efforts will lead to the abandonment of FGM and the creation of societies where the rights and dignity of every individual are respected and protected.

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